

1 **BATF3 exerts influence over exhaustion through regulation of PDCD1 and LAG3.**

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6 The exhaustion program, classically understood as a cellular state that emerges following chronic viral
7 infections or following exposure to the tumor environment, is controlled by a group of nuclear effectors that
8 includes the thymocyte selection TOX factors, IKZF family IKZF1-4, Themis, Eomes, and the BATF
9 transcription factors BATF1-3. To describe the complete extent of BATF3 gene regulation, we measured
10 total transcription in cells genetically depleted of *BATF3*. Loss of BATF3 resulted in induction of *PDCD1*
11 and *LAG3*. The interferon system was a target of BATF transcriptional control. BATF3 depletion activated
12 *MX1* and results in induction of interferon gamma (*IFNG*), *IFI44L* and *OAS1*. However, BATF3 depletion
13 resulted in loss of *IFNGR2* expression. BATF3 control of basic cytotoxic cell functions was evidenced by
14 activation of granzymes *GZMB* and *GZMH* following BATF3 depletion. Cell surface marker regulation by
15 BATF3 included induction of CD81 and CD70 and loss of CD96. Natural killer function regulation by
16 BATF3 was illustrated by activation of *NKG7* following BATF3 depletion. A specific profile of cytokine
17 regulation by BATF3 was observed. BATF3 depletion resulted in activation of *IL13* and *CXCR3*, *CCL20*
18 and *CCL5*. *IL16* expression was lost in cells depleted of BATF3. Nuclear factors of the exhaustion
19 program exert control over more than just cell surface exhaustion marker; BATF3 controls a diverse
20 collection of molecules with immune function including granzyme-based cytotoxicity, regulation of the
21 cytokines IL-13 and IL-16, and suppression of natural killer cell function.
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